

Synthesis of Possible Antiamoebic Agents. Part II

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Synthesis of 2-*p*-dimethylaminoethyl-3-alkyl-6-methoxyquinolines with alkyl groups (Me, Et, and *n*-Pr) has been effected with a view to testing the amoebacidal activity of the resulting products.

Based on the pronounced amoebacidal activity of halo-8-hydroxyquinolines, Burkhalter and Edgerton¹ synthesised several substituted 8-quinolinols possessing a basic side chain attached to the nucleus. Out of these, 5-chloro-7-diethylaminomethyl-8-quinolinol was shown by Thompson *et al.*² to possess higher *in vitro* and *in vivo* amoebacidal activity than that of di-iodoquine. Later Burkhalter *et al.*³ have reported 5-chloro-7-(3-diethylaminopropylaminomethyl)-8-quinolinol (PAA 3854 or Kan 322) as a highly potential amoebicide. Kaushiva⁴ observed *in vitro* activity of this compound against *E. histolytica* and *E. invadens*, comparable to that of 4-(*p*-chlorophenylamino)-6-methoxy-8-quinolinaldol. With a view to ascertaining the utility of 8-OH group for the amoebacidal activity, the synthesis of compounds of the type (IV) has been undertaken. These compounds have been synthesised by the route shown below.

2-Methyl-3-alkyl-4-hydroxy-6-methoxyquinolines (I) were synthesised in very good yields by condensing *p*-anisidine with alkyl acetoacetic ester by the Conard-Limpach reaction, according to the method adopted by Stephen and co-workers⁵ for the preparation

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4837.
2. *Amer. J. Trop. Med.*, 1955, 4, 224.
3. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1327.
4. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19C, 204.
5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1034.

of 4-hydroxy-6-methoxy-3-ethylquinoline. These were converted to substituted 4-chloroquinolines (II) in fairly good yields. The chlorination was achieved by a mixture of POCl_3 and PCl_5 according to Pathak and Pathak⁶ for the preparation of 2-methyl-3-alkyl-4-chloro-6-methoxyquinolines. On hydrogenation under pressure in presence of palladium-charcoal catalyst, dechlorination of the compounds was effected to provide compounds of type (III), which on subjecting to the Mannich reaction yielded the desired 2- β -dimethylaminoethyl-3-alkyl-6-methoxyquinolines (IV) in moderate yields.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methyl-3-alkyl-4-hydroxy-6-methoxyquinoline (I: R=Me, Et & n -Pr).—A mixture of *p*-anisidine (12.3 g., 0.1M), 2-alkylacetoacetic ester (0.11M), a few drops of HCl (conc.), and benzene (ca. 50 ml) was kept overnight; it was then heated in an oil bath at 120-30° in a Dean-Stark apparatus till no more water had collected. Benzene was then distilled in an oil bath. The residual viscous mass was poured on boiling diphenyl oxide (ca. 200 ml). After boiling for 15 to 20 min. the mass was cooled, diluted with petroleum (b. p. 60-80°) and left overnight. It was then filtered and washed with light petroleum. The crude product was crystallised from ethanol.

2-Methyl-3-alkyl-4-chloro-6-methoxyquinoline (II: R=Me, Et & n -Pr).—A mixture of 2-methyl-3-alkyl-4-hydroxy-6-methoxyquinoline (I, 0.7M), PCl_5 (0.01M, 3 g.), and POCl_3 (0.2M, 35 ml) was heated in an oil bath at 120-25° for 3 hr. The product was cooled and poured on crushed ice. The aqueous solution was neutralised with liquor ammonia under cooling till distinctly alkaline. The solid mass separating was filtered and dissolved in HCl (dil.). The impurities were removed by extracting with benzene. The acidic layer was clarified by animal charcoal, filtered and then basified with liquor ammonia under cooling. The chloro compound separated as a crystalline mass. The product was recrystallised from ethanol.

2-Methyl-3-alkyl-6-methoxyquinoline (III: R=Me, Et & n -Pr).—A mixture of the preceding compound (II, 0.01M), anhydrous sodium acetate (1.02 g., 0.01M), glacial acetic acid (20 ml), and Pd-C (0.5 g.) as a catalyst was taken in a reduction chamber of the hydrogenation plant. A constant current of hydrogen gas was passed through the mixture under 60 lb./sq. inch pressure while the contents were stirred constantly with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The dechlorination was completed after 24 hr. The solution was taken out and the catalyst was filtered and washed with dilute acetic acid. On neutralising the filtrate with KOH solution under cooling, a solid mass separated. It was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. In the case of (III: R= n -Pr), the resulting product was an oil. It was extracted with benzene. After removal of the benzene the residual oil was distilled.

2- β -Dimethylaminoethyl-3-alkyl-6-methoxyquinoline (IV: R=Me, Et & n -Pr).—A mixture of 2-methyl-3-alkyl-6-methoxyquinoline (0.01M), paraformaldehyde (0.2M, 0.8 g.), and dimethylamine hydrochloride (0.008M, 0.8 g.) was just dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (2.5 ml) and then 2 drops of HCl (conc.) were added. The contents were refined on a water

bath for about an hour and then a further amount of paraformaldehyde (0.1M, 0.4g.) was added and heating continued for 2 hr. more. After the reaction was over, the ethanol was distilled. The residual mass was dissolved in water and basified with NaOH solution. The base was extracted with benzene and the extract was washed with water. On removal of the benzene, the base was obtained as a viscous mass.

The *picrate*, prepared in the usual manner from ethanolic solution, was crystallized from anhydrous ethanol.

TABLE I

R.	% Yield.	M.P. or B.P.	Picrate M.P.	Formula. (Base)	% Nitrogen.		% Chlorine.		% OMe.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
2-Methyl-3-alkyl-4-hydroxy-6-methoxyquinoline (I).										
Me	78.8	287°	182°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	6.78	6.89			15.00 ^r	15.20
Et	92.0	288°	222°	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	6.35	6.45			14.00	14.20
n-Pr	73.5	260°	210°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	5.96	6.06			13.10	13.40
2-Methyl-3-alkyl-4-chloro-6-methoxyquinoline (II).										
Me	42.3	235°	215°	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ONCl	6.11	6.32	15.80	16.02	13.70	13.90
Et	86.8	283	210°	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ONCl	5.60	5.90	14.80	15.00	13.00	13.10
n-Pr	49.6	275°	188°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ONCl	5.40	5.61	14.00	14.20	12.20	12.40
2-Methyl-3-alkyl-6-methoxyquinoline (III).										
Me	66.6	78°	200°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ON	7.35	7.43			16.40	16.50
Et	60.0	76°	206°	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ON	6.74	6.96			15.10	15.40
n-Pr	45.8	155°/3mm	223°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON	6.33	6.51			14.10	14.40
2-β-Dimethylaminoethyl-3-alkyl-6-methoxyquinoline (IV). Picrates.										
Me	38.0		131°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂	14.50	14.70			6.30	6.50
Et	33.7		162°	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂	14.20	14.30			6.25	6.36
n-Pr	41.6		205°	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂	13.60	13.90			5.90	6.18

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. Shiv Mangal Singh 'Suman', Principal, Madhav College, Ujjain, for providing research facilities and to Dr. C. N. Kaohru, Reader, Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu & Kashmir, for his keen interest during the course of the investigation.